

THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC VIGILANCE ON ORGANIZATIONAL INGENUITY IN YEMEN'S MOBILE PHONE COMPANIES

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Abstract

The study aimed to measure the impact of strategic vigilance on regulatory ingenuity in the Yemen's mobile phone companies. The identification tool was based on a random cast eye of 220 workers. The results of the study were as follows: The level of strategic vigilance in Yemen's mobile phone companies from the overall point of view of workers was high, with an average calculation of (5.36) With a standard deviation (0.71 and 76.57%, the results of the study also showed that the level of organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies from the overall point of view of workers was high, with an average calculation of (5.14) with standard deviation (0.83) and 73.43%, and a statistically significant effect at a level ($0.05 \geq \alpha$) strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) over the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies.

Keywords: Strategic Vigilance, Organizational Ingenuity.

The problem of the study and its questions:

Yemen's mobile phone companies faces instability in a way that limits its ability to adapt to environmental variables and effects As a result of Yemen's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) as it will become an open market for the products and services of WTO members, this has posed a new challenge for Yemen's mobile phone companies, and they must adopt modern management methods such as strategic vigilance and regulatory prowess, Based on the foregoing, the study's problem can be elaborated in the following main question: What is the impact of strategic vigilance on Yemen's organizational ingenuity in the mobile phone companies? 1- Does strategic vigilance in its dimensions of (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) affect organizational ingenuity in its combined dimensions of (exploitation of opportunities, search for new opportunities, structural flexibility) in Yemen's mobile phone companies? The problem of the study can be clarified by asking the following President: What has the impact of strategic vigilance on the organizational ingenuity in the Yemeni mobile phone companies? Study hypotheses: Through the problem and questions of the study and its objectives and after examining the theoretical basis of the relevant study variables, the relationship between the study variables and the hypotheses was identified as the initial solution to the problem which will be tested and validated in different methods and methods as explained:

Study Society:

The study community means the total group of persons to whom the researcher seeks to generalize the results. The study community consists of 515 workers as shown in the following table:

Table (1): Number of mobile phone company employees studied

Management Level	Yemen Mobile	YOU	Saba Phone	Y Company	Total
Executive Director	1	1	1	1	4
Deputies	3	9			12
General Managers			5		5
Director of Management	15	84	59	25	183
Head of Section	62	123	97	29	311
Total	81	217	162	55	515

Source: (HR data)

The randomized class sample was selected in the application of this study for the presence of study targets at different management levels in the companies under consideration. The sample size was determined in accordance with the Morgen Rule. The total number of study community is 515 Executive Director, Deputy Executive Director, General Director, Management Director, Head of Department. The total sample size according to the Morgen Rule is 220 workers and workers distributed as follows: (35 from Yemen Mobile, 93 from YOU, 69 from Spa Phone, 23 from Y company (Y) at various administrative levels, and the distribution of the sample at each management level in the companies studied can be explained according to Table (2) Sample size in the companies studies

Table (2): Sample study in Yemen's mobile phone companies surveyed

Management Level	Yemen mobile	YOU	Saba Phone	Y Company	Total
Total Community	81	217	162	55	515
Relative Sample	35	93	69	23	220

Source: Researcher by study sample type (relative sample)

In order to achieve the specific sample and to anticipate a loss in the returned questionnaires, 240 questionnaires were distributed. The number of analytical questionnaires (220) reached a verification rate of 95.40% of the sample required for the study, and table (3) details the distribution, recovery and analysis of the questionnaires

Table (3): Distribution, recovery and analysis of questionnaires

Company Name	Distributed questionnaires	Recovered questionnaires	Damaged questionnaires	Analytical questionnaires
Yemen mobile	45	35	0	35
YOU	95	94	1	93
Saba Fone	75	71	2	69
Y Company	25	24	1	23
Total	240	224	4	220

Source: Prepared by the researcher

Main hypothesis:

There is no statistically significant effect at the $(0.05 \geq \alpha)$ level of strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance — commercial vigilance — environmental vigilance — competitive vigilance) in the organizational ingenuity in its combined dimensions in the Yemeni mobile phone companies. This hypothesis derives from sub-hypotheses: There is no statistically significant impact of technological vigilance on the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies. There is no statistically significant impact of commercial vigilance on the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies. There is no statistically significant impact of environmental vigilance on the organizational this demonstrates the importance of strategic vigilance in attention to and awareness of current events and internal and external experiences, creating and utilizing opportunities and avoiding the effects of potential threats on Yemeni mobile companies' regulatory prowess. This allows it to strengthen strategies to exploit opportunities and seek new opportunities and flexibility in the organizational structure, through optimal use of all ideas and skills provided by staff as well as clients. This can be achieved through the operationalization of mechanisms that encourage the exchange of ideas, discussion sessions and workshops, as well as through the provision of material and moral rewards to individuals who come up with new creative ideas. This demonstrates the importance of strategic vigilance in attention to and awareness of current events and internal and external experiences, creating and utilizing opportunities and avoiding the effects of potential threats on Yemeni mobile companies' regulatory prowess. This allows it to strengthen strategies to exploit opportunities and seek new opportunities and flexibility in the organizational structure, through optimal use of all ideas and skills provided by staff as well as clients. This can be achieved through the operationalization of mechanisms that encourage the exchange of ideas, discussion sessions and workshops, as well as through the provision of material and moral rewards to individuals who come up with new creative ideas. ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies. There is no statistically significant impact of competitive vigilance on the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies. The two researchers summarize the answer to the second question, which states: What level of organizational ingenuity is available from the point of view of telecommunications workers? The following table

Table (04): Computational averages and standard deviations of the average responses of members of the study sample about the degree of availability Strategic vigilance in Yemen's mobile phone companies

Order Dimensions	Dimension	Arithmetic Average	Standard deviation	Percentage	Level of availability
1	Technological vigilance	5.47	0.75	78.14%	High
2	Marketing Vigilance	5.46	0.85	78.00%	High
3	Competitive vigilance	5.27	0.8	75.29%	High
4	Environmental vigilance	5.23	0.84	74.71%	High
Overall average axis (strategic vigilance)		5.36	0.71	76.57%	High

Through table (04), the highest degree of strategic vigilance in the Yemeni mobile phone companies was found to be in the technological vigilance dimension, with an average calculation (5.47) by standard deviation (0.75) by 78.14% and at a high level, the second order came after marketing vigilance, with an average calculation (5.46) by standard deviation (0.85) and a ratio (78.00%) At a high level, in the third order, the competitive vigilance dimension came, with an average calculation (5.27) with a standard deviation (0.80) and a ratio (75.29%). At a high level, the fourth and final order came after environmental vigilance, with an average calculation (5.23) of standard deviation (0.84) and 74.71%, at a high level .Overall, the results showed that the degree of strategic vigilance in the Yemeni mobile phone companies is high, with an average calculation (5.36) of a standard deviation (0.71) and a ratio of 76.57%, and the researcher attributes this to This demonstrates the importance of strategic vigilance in attention to and awareness of current events and internal and external experiences, creating and utilizing opportunities and avoiding the effects of potential threats on Yemeni mobile companies' regulatory prowess. This allows it to strengthen strategies to exploit opportunities and seek new opportunities and flexibility in the organizational structure, through optimal use of all ideas and skills provided by staff as well as clients. This can be achieved through the operationalization of mechanisms that encourage the exchange of ideas, discussion sessions and workshops, as well as through the provision of material and moral rewards to individuals who come up with new creative ideas.

Table (05): Computational averages and standard deviations of the average responses of the study sample individuals on the dimensions of the second axis (organizational ingenuity) and the overall average axis

Order Dimensions	Dimension	Arithmetic Average	Standard deviation	Percentage	Level of availability
1	exploit the opportunities	5.28	0.87	75.43%	High
2	Find New Opportunities	5.23	0.86	74.71%	High
3	Flexible organizational structure	4.91	1.08	70.14%	High
Total average dimensions (organizational ingenuity)		5.14	0.83	73.43%	High

Table (05) shows the following: The highest level of organizational ingenuity in the Yemen's mobile phone companies is the dimension of the exploitation of opportunities, with an average calculation (5.28) of a standard deviation (0.87). (75.43%) At a high level, the second order came after the search for new opportunities, with an average account (5.23) with a standard deviation (0.86) and a ratio (74.71%) At a high level, in the third and final order, there was a flexible organizational structure, with an average calculation (4.91) with a standard deviation (1.08) and a ratio (70.14%) at a high level. The results also show that Yemen's mobile phone companies has a high level of organizational ingenuity, with an average calculation (5.14) of a standard deviation (0.83) and a ratio of 73.43% .Test the validity of the study hypotheses: Main hypothesis: There is no statistically significant effect at the indicative level (0.05) of strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) in Yemen's mobile phone companies' regulatory prowess.

As mentioned above, this hypothesis has four partial hypotheses, each tested separately, and the researcher has addressed the hypothesis test in terms of the effect of the independent variable as a whole with the dependent variable, and then the effect of each dimension of the independent variable. (Strategic vigilance) on organizational ingenuity individually as stipulated in the sub-hypotheses. The researcher addressed this in some detail:

Table (06): showing linear regression coefficient Simple between independent variable (strategic vigilance) and dependent variable (organizational ingenuity)

Independent Variable: Strategic vigilance	Dependent Variable: Organizational ingenuity						
	Form Summary		Variation Test Results (ANOVA)		Regression coefficient and test results (T)		
	Link Lab R	Determination coefficient R ²	Value (F)	Indicative level Sig.	Beta Impact Score	Value (T)	Value (F)
	0.802	0.644	394.039	0.000	0.942	19.85	0.000

Through the previous table (06), the results of simple linear regression showed a statistically significant relationship to the effect of the independent variable (strategic vigilance) on the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity), with an R = 0.802 correlation factor. It is a positive correlation coefficient with a large expulsion relationship that has a statistically significant connotation level (0.000), as indicated by the results of the determination coefficient of R² = 0.644. 64.4% of changes (variability) on organizational ingenuity are mainly due to the independent variable strategic vigilance, while 25.6% of retention is for variability in changes in desire Regulatory is due to other variables, and the degree of effect (regression coefficient) is Predictive ($\beta=0.942$), meaning that improvement in strategic vigilance to a single degree results in an improvement on organizational ingenuity by 94.2%. It also confirms the morale of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the calculated F value, at (394,039), as well as the calculated T value of (19,850) and at an indicative level (0.000) below the level of moral indication (0.05).

From the above and through the coefficient of binding between the two variables (R), the determining factor (R²), the regression factor (β), the value (F), the value (T) and the level of statistical indication, based on the above, we conclude the validity of the main hypothesis, so it is accepted that: there is a statistically significant effect at the level of the Indicative (0.05) of strategic vigilance on organizational ingenuity, and the level of that impact is significant.

The role of the dimensions of the independent variable on the variable has also been ascertained sub assumptions, as follows Sub-hypothesis 1: There is no statistically significant effect at the 0.05 level of technological vigilance in Yemen's mobile phone companies' organizational ingenuity. To test the validity of the hypothesis, the researcher uses a simple linear regression test, to ascertain the effect of the independent variable (technological vigilance) on the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity). The results were as shown in the following table: Table (04) shows the simple linear regression factor between the independent variable.

Table (07): shows the simple linear regression factor between the independent variable (technological vigilance) and the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity)

Independent Variable: Technological vigilance	Dependent Variable: Organizational ingenuity						
	Form Summary		Variation Test Results (ANOVA)		Regression coefficient and test results (T)		
	Link Lab R	Determination coefficient R ²	Value (F)	Indicative level Sig.	Beta Impact Score	Value (T)	Value (F)
	0.63	0.397	143.493	0	0.63	0.397	143.493

Through the previous table (07), the results of simple linear regression showed a statistically significant relationship to the effect of the independent variable (Technological vigilance) on the dependent variable (regulatory prowess), with an $R = 0.630$ correlation factor. It is a positive correlation coefficient with a large expulsion relationship that has a statistically significant connotation level (0.000), as the results of the determination coefficient of $R^2 = 0.397$ indicate. 39.7% of changes on organizational ingenuity are due mainly to the independent variable of technological vigilance, while (60.3%) of the veins for variability in changes on organizational ingenuity is due to other variables, as has the degree of impact. The predictive ($\beta=0.697$) regression coefficient means that the improvement in the application of technology vigilance to a single degree results in an improvement on organizational ingenuity of 69.7%. It also confirms the morale of the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the calculated F value (143.493), as well as the calculated T value (11.979) at an indicative level (0.000) below the level of moral indication (0.05). This is through the coefficient of association between the two variables (R), the determination factor (R²), the regression coefficient (β), the value (F), the value (T) and the level of statistical indication, and based on the above we conclude the validity of the first sub-hypothesis, which is accepted by the second sub-hypothesis: there is a statistically significant effect at the level of (0.05) marketing vigilance in the Yemeni companies. To test the validity of the hypothesis, the researcher uses a simple linear regression test, to ascertain the effect of the independent variable (marketing vigilance) in the variable Subordinate (organizational ingenuity). The results were as shown in the following table:

Table (08): shows the simple linear regression factor between the independent variable (marketing vigilance) and the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity)

Independent Variable: Marketing vigilance	Dependent Variable: Organizational ingenuity						
	Form Summary Link Lab	Variation Test Results (ANOVA)	Regression coefficient and test results (T)		Technological vigilance		
			Value (F)	Indicative level Sig.	Beta Impact Score	Value (T)	Value (F)
	0.693	0.48	201.495	0.000	0.676	14.195	0.000

Through the previous table (08) the results of simple linear regression showed a statistically significant relationship to the effect of the independent variable (Marketing vigilance) on the dependent variable (regulatory prowess), with an $R = 0.693$ correlation factor. It is a positive correlation coefficient with a large expulsive relationship that has a statistically significant connotation level (0.000), as the results of the determination coefficient of $R^2 = 0.480$ indicate. 48.0% of changes on organizational appetite are due mainly to the independent variable of marketing vigilance, while (52.0%) of the thresholds for variability in changes in the achievement of organizational ingenuity is due to other variables, as has the degree of impact. The predictive ($\beta=0.676$) regression coefficient means that improvement in the application of marketing vigilance to a single degree results in an improvement on organizational ingenuity of 67.6%. It also confirms the morale of the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the calculated F value (201.495), as well as the calculated T value (14.196) at an indicative level (0.000) below the level of morale 0.05. From the foregoing and through the coefficient of association between the two variables (R), the determining factor (R^2), the regression factor (β), the value (F), the value (T) and the level of statistical indication, based on the foregoing we conclude the validity of the first zero sub-hypothesis, it is rejected which states that: There is no statistically significant effect at an indicative level (0.05) for marketing vigilance in achieving organizational ingenuity in the Yemen's mobile phone companies and accepting the alternative hypothesis that: A statistically significant effect exists at an indicative level (0.05) of marketing vigilance in achieving organizational ingenuity on the mobile phone companies and is significant. Sub-hypothesis III: There is no statistically significant effect at the 0.05 level of competitive vigilance in the Yemeni companies's regulatory prowess. To test hypothesis validity, I use a test researcher. Simple linear regression, to ascertain the effect of the independent variable (technological vigilance) on the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity). The results were as shown in the following table

Table (09): shows the simple linear regression factor between the independent variable (competitive vigilance) and the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity)

Independent Variable: Competitive vigilance	Dependent Variable: Organizational ingenuity						
	Form Summary Link Lab	Variation Test Results (ANOVA)	Regression coefficient and test results (T)		Technological vigilance		
			Value (F)	Indicative level Sig.	Beta Impact Score	Value (T)	Value (F)
	0.693	0.48	201.495	0.000	0.676	14.195	0.000

Through the previous table (09), the results of the simple linear regression showed a statistically significant link to the effect of the independent variable (competitive vigilance) on the subordinate variable (regulatory prowess), with an $R = 0.765$ correlation factor, a positive correlation factor with a statistically significant exclusive relationship. Indicative level (0.000), as indicated by $R^2 = 0.586$ determination factor results 58.6% of changes on organizational ingenuity are due mainly to the independent variable of competitive vigilance, while (41.4%) of the veins for variability in changes on organizational ingenuity is due to other variables, as

has the degree of impact Predictive ($\beta=0.795$) regression coefficient means that improvement in the application of competitive vigilance with a single degree results in an improvement on organizational ingenuity by 79.5%. It also confirms the morale of the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the calculated F value (308.114), as well as the calculated T value (17.553) at an indicative level (0.000) below the level of moral indication (0.05). From the foregoing and through the coefficient of binding between the two variables (R), the determination factor (R^2), the regression factor (β), the value (F), the value (T) and the level of statistical indication, based on the above we wrongly conclude the first zero sub-hypothesis, so it is rejected which states that: There is a statistically significant impact at an indicative level (0.05) of competitive vigilance in achieving organizational ingenuity in Yemen's telecommunications companies, which is significant. Sub-hypothesis II: There is no statistically significant effect at the 0.05 level of marketing vigilance in the Yemeni companies' regulatory prowess. To test the validity of the hypothesis, the researcher uses a simple linear regression test, to ascertain the effect of the independent variable (marketing vigilance) on the dependent variable regulatory prowess). The results were as shown in the following table:

Table (10): shows the simple linear regression coefficient between the independent variable environmental vigilance and dependent variability (organizational ingenuity)

Independent Variable: Environmental vigilance	Dependent Variable: Organizational ingenuity						
	Form Summary Link Lab	Variation Test Results (ANOVA)	Regression coefficient and test results (T)		Technological vigilance		
					Beta Impact Score	Value (T)	Value (F)
	0.712	0.506	223.734	0	0.707	14.958	0

Through Table (10) the results of simple linear regression showed a statistically significant relationship to the effect of the independent variable (Environmental vigilance) on the dependent variable (regulatory prowess), with the correlation factor $R = 0.712$. It is a positive correlation coefficient with a large expulsion relationship that has a statistically significant connotation level (0.000), as the results of the determination coefficient of $R^2 = 0.506$ indicate. 50.6% of changes (variability) on organizational ingenuity are due mainly to the independent variable of environmental vigilance, while (49.4%) of the thresholds for variability in changes on organizational ingenuity is due to other variables, and has reached the degree of impact Predictive ($\beta=0.707$) regression coefficient. This means that the improvement in the application of single-degree environmental vigilance results in an improvement on organizational ingenuity of 70.7%. It also confirms the morale of the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable, the calculated F value, where the (223.734), as well as T's calculated value of 14.958 at an indicative level (0.000) below the moral connotation level (0.05). From the above and through the coefficient of binding between the two variables (R), the determining factor (R^2), the regression factor (β), the value (F), the value (T) and the level of statistical indication, based on the above we wrongly conclude the first sub-hypothesis, so it is rejected, which states that: There is no statistically significant effect at an indicative level (0.05) of environmental vigilance in investigating the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies and accepting the alternative hypothesis that: There is no statistically significant

impact at an indicative level (0.05) of environmental vigilance in an investigation into Yemen's organizational ingenuity in the telecommunications companies, which is significant. In order to ascertain the extent to which the dimensions of the independent variable affect strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) combined on the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity), the researcher used a multiple linear regression test, the results as shown in the table below.

Table (11): The results of the multiple linear regression analysis of the impact of variable dimensions (strategic vigilance) combined on organizational ingenuity

Summary of Forms				Disparity Analysis ANOVA		Regression and Test (T)			Transactions Variance inflation factors VIF
Affiliate Variable	Dimensions of independent variable (Information technology)	Binding coefficient R	Determination coefficient R2	Value (F)	Indicative level	Value B	Value (T)	Indicative level	
Organizational ingenuity	Technological vigilance	0.813	0.661	104.764	0.000	0.151	2.284	0.023	Organizational ingenuity
	Marketing Vigilance					0.131	1.928	0.055	3.868
	Competitive vigilance					0.427	6.191	0.000	3.060
	Environmental vigilance					0.234	3.770	0.000	3.150

The results in table (11) showed that: the value of the relationship between the dimensions of the independent variable (strategic vigilance) combined and the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity) was positive, with the value of the correlation coefficient (0.813), a significant positive expulsion relationship. It also confirms the morale of the influential relationship between the two variables the value (F) of 104.764 and the level of indication (0.000), which confirms the efficiency of the independent variables combined in the interpretation of the dependent variable (organizational ingenuity), in addition to the value of the determination coefficient ($R^2 = 0.661$) which shows that the dimensions of the independent variable (Strategic vigilance) combined interprets (66.1%) variability in variables on organizational ingenuity, while retention (33.9%) Changes on organizational ingenuity are attributable to factors other than strategic vigilance. This indicates that strategic vigilance is an important factor of organizational ingenuity and that the higher the level of improvement in strategic vigilance, the greater the achievement of organizational ingenuity in Yemen's telecommunications companies. The regression factors also demonstrate the relative importance of the dimensions of the independent variable when they both influence the level of organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies and are combined as follows: Statistically significant impact of dimensional interaction (technological vigilance, competitive vigilance, environmental vigilance) the results showed that the beta impact rate (β) was (0.151, 0.427, 0.234) respectively and at an indicative level (0.023, 0.000 and 0.000), respectively, below the level of moral significance (0.05). This result indicates that, assuming the effect of any other variables is neutralized, the increase would be in the level of improvement (Technological vigilance, competitive vigilance, environmental vigilance) one degree leads to

an increase of (81.2%) In achieving organizational ingenuity, the competitive environmental vigilance dimension was found to be the most influential dimension followed by the environmental vigilance dimension, then the technological vigilance dimension, and finally the marketing vigilance dimension, as the dimension (Marketing vigilance) has a weak effect when these factors come together with each other. Based on the foregoing, the main zero hypothesis that: There is no statistically significant effect at an indicative level (0.05) of strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) on organizational ingenuity and acceptance of the main alternative hypothesis that: There is a statistically significant effect at an indicative level (0.05) of strategic vigilance in its dimensions (technological vigilance, commercial vigilance, environmental vigilance, competitive vigilance) in the organizational ingenuity in Yemen's telecommunications companies, which is significant.

The recommendations:

Some of the recommendations to be considered are as follows

- Increased strategic vigilance and investment on organizational ingenuity in Yemen's mobile phone companies.
- Improve communications infrastructure and provide modern and sophisticated equipment and devices to improve in Yemen's mobile phone companies
- Develop companions' workers' skill levels and organize training courses and workshops to improve the level of skills needed for strategic vigilance work.
- Develop databases and improve the information storage and retrieval system to improve the availability of regulatory capabilities in this companies.
- Improve the companies' organizational preparation and develop the organizational structure of companies and institutions to improve their ability to make strategic decisions.
- Work to develop the positive relationship between strategic vigilance and organizational ingenuity, and identify the most influential factors in this relationship.
- Contribute to research and development in the field of strategic monitoring and organizational capacity, exchange experiences and knowledge with various companies and institutions in this companies.
- Promote innovation, develop strategic vigilance and improve its use in companies and institutions and enhance resilience to changes in the external environment.
- Improve the internal and external operations of companies and institutions in the telecommunications companies, improve the quality of services provided to customers and provide innovative and high-quality services.
- Develop performance indicators and evaluate performance periodically to improve the technical and management level in the mobile phone companies.

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